

ASAP Lines

hPSCs	Origin of Line	Original Cell type	Status	Demographics	Citation	Features	Modified by	Funding
NH50188 (GBA)	NINDS	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (GBA N370S/isogenic)	XY, Caucasian				
NH50186 (GBA)	NINDS	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (GBA N370S/isogenic)	XY, Caucasian				
NH50187 (GBA)	NINDS	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (GBA N370S/isogenic)	XY, Caucasian				
NH50186-THTdT (GBA)	NINDS	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (GBA N370S/isogenic)	XY, Caucasian				
NH50188-THTdT (GBA)	NINDS	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (GBA N370S/isogenic)	XY, Caucasian				
4-copy-SNCA_S3-W	Whitehead Institute	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (SNCA	XY, Caucasian				ASAP-Studer

- D9			triplication)					
4-copy-SNCA_S3-W - G8	Whitehead Institute	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (SNCA triplication)	XY, Caucasian				ASAP-Studer
2-copy-SNCA_S3-W - F2	Whitehead Institute	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (SNCA triplication)	XY, Caucasian				ASAP-Studer
2-copy-SNCA_S3-W - H6	Whitehead Institute	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (SNCA triplication)	XY, Caucasian				ASAP-Studer
0-copy-SNCA_S3-W - E9	Whitehead Institute	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (SNCA triplication)	XY, Caucasian				ASAP-Studer
4-copy-SNCA_S3-C	Whitehead Institute	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (SNCA triplication)	XX, Caucasian				ASAP-Studer
4-copy-SNCA_S3-C - E7	Whitehead Institute	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (SNCA triplication)	XX, Caucasian				ASAP-Studer
2-copy-SNCA_S3-C - C6	Coriell Institute	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (SNCA triplication)	XX, Caucasian				ASAP-Studer
2-copy-SNCA_S3-C - D3	Whitehead Institute	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (SNCA triplication)	XX, Caucasian				ASAP-Studer
2-copy-SNCA_S3-C - D9	Whitehead Institute	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (SNCA triplication)	XX, Caucasian				ASAP-Studer

0-copy- SNCA_S3-C - E2	Coriell Institute	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (SNCA triplication)	XX, Caucasian				ASAP- Studer
4-copy- SNCA_AST23	Tilo Kunath	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (SNCA triplication)	XX, Caucasian	Chen et al EJN 2018			
2-copy- SNCA_AST23	Tilo Kunath	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (SNCA triplication)	XX, Caucasian	Chen et al EJN 2018			
0-copy- SNCA_AST23	Tilo Kunath	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (SNCA triplication)	XX, Caucasian	Chen et al EJN 2018			
MSK-SRF1 + iCas9	Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center	urinary tract epithelial cell	Apparently Healthy	XX, Asian		AAVS1- inducible Cas9		ASAP- Studer
MSK-SRF1 + iCas9 LRRK2 #14	Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center	urinary tract epithelial cell	Apparently Healthy (LRRK2 G2019S engineered)	XX, Asian		AAVS1- inducible Cas9		ASAP- Studer
MSK-SRF1 + iCas9 GBA #19	Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center	urinary tract epithelial cell	Apparently Healthy (GBA N370S) engineered)	XX, Asian		AAVS1- inducible Cas9		ASAP- Studer
MSK-SRF1 + iCas9 SNCA A53T #15.1	Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center	urinary tract epithelial cell	Apparently Healthy (SNCA A53T) engineered)	XX, Asian		AAVS1- inducible Cas9		ASAP- Studer
H9 + iCas9	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	not determined	XY, Caucasian		AAVS1- inducible Cas9		ASAP- Studer

H9 + iCas9 LRRK2	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	not determined (LRRK2 G2019S engineered)	XY, Caucasian		AAVS1- inducible Cas9		ASAP- Studer
H9 + iCas9 GBA	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	not determined (GBA N370S engineered)	XY, Caucasian		AAVS1- inducible Cas9		ASAP- Studer
H9 + iCas9 SNCA A53T	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	not determined (SNCA A53T engineered)	XY, Caucasian		AAVS1- inducible Cas9		ASAP- Studer
H9 Nurr1- GFP	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	not determined	XY, Caucasian	Kim et al. Cell Stem Cell 2021	AAVS1- inducible Cas9		
H9 Nurr1- GFP LRRK2	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	not determined (LRRK2 G2019S engineered)	XY, Caucasian		AAVS1- inducible Cas9		
PDD-1	Mass General Brigham SCiN	Fibroblasts	Sporadic LBD	X,Y				
DLB-2	Mass General Brigham SCiN	Fibroblasts	Sporadic LBD	X,Y				
PDD-2	Mass General Brigham SCiN	Fibroblasts	Sporadic LBD	X,Y				
PD2-2 GBA 2/6 pB-rtTA (#4)-NGN2- puro-SNAP	German Center for Neurodegenerative Diseases	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (GBA (L444P))	X,Y	Schöndorf et al. Nat Comm 2014, Hallacli et al. Cell 2022	pB-rtTA (#4)- NGN2-puro- SNAP	BWH	ASAP- Studer

PD2-2 GC2 GBA 2/7 pB- rtTA (#4)- NGN2-puro- SNAP	German Center for Neurodegenerative Diseases	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (GBA (L444P) corrected)	X,Y	Schöndorf et al. Nat Comm 2014, Hallacli et al. Cell 2022	pB-rtTA (#4)- NGN2-puro- SNAP	BWH	ASAP- Studer
LRRK2-GS-1, T4.6mut pB- rtTA (#4)- NGN2-puro- SNAP	German Center for Neurodegenerative Diseases	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (LRRK2 (G2019S))	X,X	Schöndorf et al. Nat Comm 2014, Hallacli et al. Cell 2022	pB-rtTA (#4)- NGN2-puro- SNAP	BWH	ASAP- Studer
LRRK2-GS-2, L2.1mut pB- rtTA (#4)- NGN2-puro- SNAP	German Center for Neurodegenerative Diseases	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (LRRK2 (G2019S))	X,X	Schöndorf et al. Nat Comm 2014, Hallacli et al. Cell 2022	pB-rtTA (#4)- NGN2-puro- SNAP	BWH	ASAP- Studer
CORR/GS-1 pB-rtTA (#4)- NGN2-puro- SNAP	German Center for Neurodegenerative Diseases	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (LRRK2 (G2019S) corrected)	X,X	Schöndorf et al. Nat Comm 2014, Hallacli et al. Cell 2022	pB-rtTA (#4)- NGN2-puro- SNAP	BWH	ASAP- Studer
CORR/GS-2 pB-rtTA (#4)- NGN2-puro- SNAP	German Center for Neurodegenerative Diseases	Fibroblasts	Parkinson's Disease (LRRK2 (G2019S) corrected)	X,X	Schöndorf et al. Nat Comm 2014,	pB-rtTA (#4)- NGN2-puro- SNAP	BWH	ASAP- Studer

					Hallacli et al. Cell 2022			
A53T-1A pB-rtTA (#4)-NGN2-puro-SNAP	Yumanity Therapeutics/BWH		Parkinson's Disease (SNCA (A53T))	X,Y		pB-rtTA (#4)-NGN2-puro-SNAP	BWH	ASAP-Studer
A53T-1C pB-rtTA (#4)-NGN2-puro-SNAP	Yumanity Therapeutics/BWH		Parkinson's Disease (SNCA (A53T))	X,Y		pB-rtTA (#4)-NGN2-puro-SNAP	BWH	ASAP-Studer
A53T-1D pB-rtTA (#4)-NGN2-puro-SNAP	Yumanity Therapeutics/BWH		Parkinson's Disease (SNCA (A53T))	X,Y		pB-rtTA (#4)-NGN2-puro-SNAP	BWH	ASAP-Studer
CORR28 (A53T-1A) pB-rtTA (#4)-NGN2-puro-SNAP	Yumanity Therapeutics/BWH		Parkinson's Disease (SNCA (A53T) corrected)	X,Y		pB-rtTA (#4)-NGN2-puro-SNAP	BWH	ASAP-Studer
CORR63 (A53T-1C) pB-rtTA (#4)-NGN2-puro-SNAP	Yumanity Therapeutics/BWH		Parkinson's Disease (SNCA (A53T) corrected)	X,Y		pB-rtTA (#4)-NGN2-puro-SNAP	BWH	ASAP-Studer
H9 hESC STMN2-A53T-sfGFP clone 4-1	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	not determined	XY, Caucasian		SNCA A53T overexpression	BWH	ASAP-Studer

H9 hESC STMN2-A53T-sfGFP clone 6-1	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	not determined	XY, Caucasian		SNCA A53T overexpression	BWH	ASAP-Studer
H9 hESC STMN2-A53T-DNAC-sfGFP clone 5-2	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	not determined	XY, Caucasian		SNCA A53T overexpression	BWH	ASAP-Studer
H9 hESC STMN2-A53T-DNAC-sfGFP clone 7-2	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	not determined	XY, Caucasian		SNCA A53T overexpression	BWH	ASAP-Studer
H9 WT clone	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series	NA	ASAP-Studer
H9 GBA-N370S HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (GBA N370S) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series	MSKCC, NYSCF	ASAP-Studer
H9 GBA-N370S HOM	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (GBA N370S) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series	MSKCC, NYSCF	ASAP-Studer
H9 LRRK2-G2019S HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (LRRK2 G2019S engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series	MSKCC, NYSCF	ASAP-Studer

H9 LRRK2-G2019S HOM	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (LRRK2 G2019S engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series	MSKCC, NYSCF	ASAP-Studer
H9 SNCA-A53T HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (SNCA A53T) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series	MSKCC, NYSCF	ASAP-Studer
H9 SCNA-A53TA HOM	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (SNCA A53T) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series	MSKCC, NYSCF	ASAP-Studer
H9 WT clone LAMP1-GFP HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + organelle GFP	NSYCF	ASAP-Studer
H9 GBA-N370S HET LAMP1-GFP HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (GBA N370S) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + organelle GFP	NSYCF	ASAP-Studer
H9 LRRK2-G2019S HET LAMP1-GFP HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (LRRK2 G2019S engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + organelle GFP	NSYCF	ASAP-Studer
H9 SNCA-A53T HET LAMP1-GFP HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (SNCA A53T) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + organelle GFP	NSYCF	ASAP-Studer
H9 WT clone TOMM20-	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series +	NSYCF	ASAP-Studer

GFP HET						organelle GFP		
H9 GBA-N370S HET TOMM20-GFP HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (GBA N370S) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + organelle GFP	NSYCF	ASAP-Studer
H9 LRRK2-G2019S HET TOMM20-GFP HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (LRRK2 G2019S engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + organelle GFP	NSYCF	ASAP-Studer
H9 SNCA-A53T HET TOMM20-GFP HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (SNCA A53T) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + organelle GFP	NSYCF	ASAP-Studer
H9 WT clone LMNB1-GFP HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + organelle GFP	NSYCF	ASAP-Studer
H9 GBA-N370S HET LMNB1-GFP HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (GBA N370S) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + organelle GFP	NSYCF	ASAP-Studer
H9 LRRK2-G2019S HET LMNB1-GFP HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (LRRK2 G2019S engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + organelle GFP	NSYCF	ASAP-Studer
H9 SNCA-A53T HET LMNB1-GFP HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (SNCA A53T) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + organelle GFP	NSYCF	ASAP-Studer

H9 WT clone ACTIN-GFP HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + organelle GFP	NSYCF	ASAP- Studer
H9 GBA- N370S HET ACTIN-GFP HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (GBA N370S) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + organelle GFP	NSYCF	ASAP- Studer
H9 LRRK2- G2019S HET ACTIN-GFP HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (LRRK2 G2019S engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + organelle GFP	NSYCF	ASAP- Studer
H9 SNCA- A53T HET ACTIN-GFP HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (SNCA A53T) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + organelle GFP	NSYCF	ASAP- Studer
H9 WT clone SNCA-HALO HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + SNCA-HALO	NSYCF	ASAP- Studer
H9 GBA- N370S HET SNCA-HALO HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (GBA N370S) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + SNCA-HALO	NSYCF	ASAP- Studer
H9 LRRK2- G2019S HET SNCA-HALO HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (LRRK2 G2019S engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + SNCA-HALO	NSYCF	ASAP- Studer
H9 SNCA- A53T HET	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (SNCA	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + SNCA-HALO	NSYCF	ASAP- Studer

WTallele- SCNA-HALO			A53T) engineered)					
H9 SNCA- A53T HET A53Tallele- SCNA-HALO	WiCell Research Institute	H9 ESC line	Apparently Healthy (SNCA A53T) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		H9 quad PD allelic series + SNCA-HALO	NSYCF	ASAP- Studer
MSK-SRF1 WT	Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center	urinary tract epithelial cell	Apparently Healthy	XX, Asian		MSK-SRF1 quad PD allelic series	NA	ASAP- Studer
MSK-SRF1 GBA-N370S- HET	Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center	urinary tract epithelial cell	Apparently Healthy (GBA N370S) engineered)	XX, Asian		MSK-SRF1 quad PD allelic series	MSKCC, NYSCF	ASAP- Studer
MSK-SRF1 GBA-N370S- HOM	Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center	urinary tract epithelial cell	Apparently Healthy (GBA N370S) engineered)	XX, Asian		MSK-SRF1 quad PD allelic series	MSKCC, NYSCF	ASAP- Studer
MSK-SRF1 LRRK2- G2019S HET	Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center	urinary tract epithelial cell	Apparently Healthy (LRRK2 G2019S engineered)	XX, Asian		MSK-SRF1 quad PD allelic series	MSKCC, NYSCF	ASAP- Studer
MSK-SRF1 LRRK2- G2019S HOM	Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center	urinary tract epithelial cell	Apparently Healthy (LRRK2 G2019S engineered)	XX, Asian		MSK-SRF1 quad PD allelic series	MSKCC, NYSCF	ASAP- Studer
MSK-SRF1 SNCA-A53T HET	Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center	urinary tract epithelial cell	Apparently Healthy (SNCA A53T) engineered)	XX, Asian		MSK-SRF1 quad PD allelic series	MSKCC, NYSCF	ASAP- Studer

MSK-SRF1 SNCA-A53T HOM	Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center	urinary tract epithelial cell	Apparently Healthy (SNCA A53T) engineered)	XX, Asian		MSK-SRF1 quad PD allelic series	MSKCC, NYSCF	ASAP- Studer
KOLF2.1J WT clone	JAX	fibroblast	Apparently Healthy	XY, Caucasian		JAX PD allelic Sereis	JAX	
KOLF2.1J GBA-N370S HET	JAX	fibroblast	Apparently Healthy (GBA N370S) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		JAX PD allelic Sereis	JAX	
KOLF2.1J GBA-N370S HOM	JAX	fibroblast	Apparently Healthy (GBA N370S) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		JAX PD allelic Sereis	JAX	
KOLF2.1J LRRK2- G2019S HET	JAX	fibroblast	Apparently Healthy (LRRK2 G2019S engineered)	XY, Caucasian		JAX PD allelic Sereis	JAX	
KOLF2.1J LRRK2- G2019S HOM	JAX	fibroblast	Apparently Healthy (LRRK2 G2019S engineered)	XY, Caucasian		JAX PD allelic Sereis	JAX	
KOLF2.1J SNCA-A53T HET	JAX	fibroblast	Apparently Healthy (SNCA A53T) engineered)	XY, Caucasian		JAX PD allelic Sereis	JAX	
KOLF2.1J SCNA-A53T HOM	JAX	fibroblast	Apparently Healthy (SNCA	XY, Caucasian		JAX PD allelic Sereis	JAX	

		A53T) engineered)						
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There are some restrictions on research that may be conducted with pluripotent stem cells. Restrictions may differ between cell lines, and the cell line owners/providers are responsible for defining the restrictions specific to their cells. The restrictions are clearly identified in the MOU-SLA, MTA and/or additional documents that correspond to a specific cell line. You must obtain these documents from the original owner prior to publication of any research using cell lines we can provide.

Connect with us: [800-525-2225](tel:800-525-2225) [Locations](#)

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